

The Interrelationship between Electrical Conductivity and Catalytic Activity of Semiconductor Oxides

A. V. Ramaswamy, P. Ratnasamy* and L. M. Yeddanapalli

Three different types of semiconductor oxides, namely, an *n*-type (ZnO), a *p*-type (NiO), and an amphoteric one (Cr₂O₃) have been examined for possible correlations between their electrical conductivity and catalytic activity. The catalytic reactions investigated are the dehydrogenation and dehydration of isopropanol (over NiO and ZnO) and the dehydrogenation of β -pinene (over Cr₂O₃). From the kinetic data the desorption of acetone and the adsorption of isopropanol are inferred to be rate-determining steps over NiO and ZnO respectively.

Impregnated SO₃ suppresses both the electrical conductivity and the catalytic activity of NiO and ZnO. Thus SO₃ increases the Fermi level in the case of NiO but suppresses that of ZnO. The dehydrogenation of isopropanol, being an acceptor reaction over ZnO, is suppressed by SO₃, which also suppresses its *n*-type conductivity. Over NiO, SO₃ functioning as donor impurity shifts the reaction to the donor class; hence the suppression of dehydrogenation as the extent of added SO₃ increases.

Chromia, in the reduced state (*n*-type semiconductivity), is more active in than the oxidised state (*p*-type semiconductivity) for the dehydrogenation of β -pinene to *p*-cymene. This indicates the acceptor type nature of the dehydrogenation reaction over chromia.

The electrical conductivity of a semiconductor oxide (*n*- or *p*-type) is determined by the relative preponderance of electrons or holes in the solid. The same electrons and holes also participate in catalytic reactions occurring at the surface of the catalysts. Thus a parallelism between changes in electrical conductivity and catalytic activity is to be expected. The relationship may be direct or inverse¹. This depends on the direction of electron transfer during the rate-determining step of the reaction and the nature of the semiconductor. Reactions in which electrons are transferred to the solid during the rate-determining step, will be accelerated if the solid is depleted of electrons. For such reactions, the correlation between catalytic activity and electrical conductivity will be direct if the solid is a *p*-type conductor and inverse if it is *n*-type. On the contrary, if electrons are transferred to the adsorbate during the rate-determining step, an *n*-type semiconductor will exhibit a direct correlation between catalytic activity and electrical conductivity. An inverse correlation will be exhibited by the *p*-type specimens. The behaviour of amphoteric semiconductors depends on whether electrons or holes are the predominant charge carrier under the given conditions.

In the present paper three different types of semiconductors, namely an *n*-type (ZnO), a *p*-type (NiO), and an amphoteric one (Cr₂O₃) have been examined for possible correlations between their catalytic and electrical properties. The dehydrogenation and dehydration of

* Present address : 42, de Croylaan, 3030, Heverlee (Louvain) Belgium.

1. F. F. Wolkenstein, 'The Electronic Theory of Catalysis on Semiconductors', Pergamon Press, New York, 1963.

isopropanol over NiO, ZnO and SO_4^{2-} doped NiO and ZnO have been investigated. The dehydrogenation of a hydrocarbon, β -pinene over chromia has also been studied. The electrical conductivity of these solids as well as changes in the electrical conductivity during the catalytic reactions have been measured. From the results an attempt has been made to correlate the electrical and catalytic properties of the oxides.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials : NiO was prepared by the decomposition of nickel carbonate at 500° . ZnO was prepared by the dehydration of the hydroxide which was obtained by the hydrolysis of $[\text{Zn}(\text{NH}_3)_6]^{2+}$ complex. Cr_2O_3 was obtained by the hydrolysis followed by dehydration of chromium nitrate. NiO was impregnated with solutions containing different amounts of nickel sulphate to obtain 0.5, 1.4, and 2.7 mole percent of SO_3 in the catalyst. Similarly ZnO containing 0.5, 1.3, and 2.8 mole percent SO_3 were prepared by impregnation with solutions of zinc sulphate. All the catalysts were powdered and compressed into pellets before use. The BET surface area and other physical properties of these catalysts are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Physical Properties of the Catalysts

Catalyst	Surface area m^2/g	Pore Volume ml/g	Average pore radius \AA	Excess oxygen atom %
NiO	21.8	0.1183	80-100	1.121
NiO+0.5 mole % SO_3	20.1	—	—	0.810
NiO+1.4 mole % SO_3	18.4	—	—	0.652
NiO+2.7 mole % SO_3	15.5	—	—	0.517
ZnO	9.2	0.1624	160	—
ZnO+0.5 mole % SO_3	11.6	—	—	—
ZnO+1.3 mole % SO_3	14.2	—	—	—
ZnO+2.8 mole % SO_3	15.8	—	—	—
Cr_2O_3	14.0	—	—	—

The catalytic reactions were carried out in a fixed bed, vertical flow reactor. Adsorption studies were carried out in a conventional BET apparatus. For conductivity measurements, the sample (60-80 mesh) was taken between two platinum electrodes fused in through the sides of the vertical flow reactor. The catalyst bed was so well set after several trial runs that the electrical resistance measured between the probes in contact with the catalyst did not vary much at any particular temperature and in the atmosphere of dry air. The electrical measurements were performed with the aid of d.c. circuits. Potential differences between probes were measured by a compensation using a VTVM (Heathkit V-7A/UK) or an oscilloscope as a zero instrument. The values of the activation energy of electrical conductivity for various catalysts in the temperature range 250° - 360° are given in Table 4.

RESULTS

Decomposition of Isopropanol

Kinetic measurements: The decomposition of isopropanol over NiO and NiO impregnated with different mole percent of SO₃ has been studied in the temperature range 250°–320°. The results are shown in Table 2. The corresponding results for ZnO and SO₃

TABLE 2

Dehydrogenation of Isopropanol over NiO and modified NiO Catalysts

$$\text{WHSV}^{-1} = 1.5 \text{ hr.}$$

Catalyst	Temp. °C	Moles per 100 moles of alcohol fed		
		Isopropanol reacted	Acetone formed	Propene formed
NiO	275	31.1	31.0	—
	290	38.2	38.0	—
	305	44.9	44.7	—
	320	55.4	55.2	—
NiO + 0.5 mole % SO ₃	275	20.7	18.2	2.5
	290	27.2	22.9	4.2
	305	36.3	30.2	6.0
	320	49.3	39.8	9.5
NiO + 1.4 mole % SO ₃	275	14.4	10.8	3.6
	290	19.6	14.5	5.0
	305	28.6	20.9	7.6
	320	41.6	30.1	10.5
NiO + 2.7 mole % SO ₃	275	9.7	4.8	4.7
	290	16.5	9.6	6.8
	305	23.5	15.4	8.9
	320	36.1	24.0	12.0

doped ZnO catalysts in the range 300°–360° are shown in Table 3. Over NiO and ZnO catalysts isopropanol is dehydrogenated to acetone and hydrogen.

Several workers² have reported the formation of propene as a dehydration product of isopropanol on ZnO along with acetone. There was no clear indication in the present studies that propene is formed. Over catalysts doped with SO₃, both dehydrogenation and dehydration occurred. Though the total amount of isopropanol undergoing decomposition is

2. See for instance, J. F. Garcia de la Banda and G. Kronnenie Orlandini, Instituto de Quimica Fisica CSIC, Tech Note 1, Madrid, 1958.

TABLE 3

*Dehydrogenation of Isopropanol over ZnO and modified ZnO Catalysts*WHSV⁻¹ = 1.5 hr.

Catalyst	Temp. °C	Moles per 100 moles of alcohol fed		
		Isopropanol reacted	Acetone formed	Propene formed
ZnO	300	21.6	21.2	—
	315	35.2	34.8	—
	330	49.7	49.1	—
	340	59.2	58.9	—
ZnO + 0.5 mole % SO ₃	300	16.8	15.6	1.1
	315	27.1	24.3	2.6
	330	38.4	34.1	4.3
	345	52.5	45.2	7.1
ZnO + 1.3 mole % SO ₃	300	11.0	8.5	2.3
	317	22.2	16.0	6.0
	335	30.2	21.0	9.0
	350	40.2	28.0	12.2
ZnO + 2.8 mole % SO ₃	300	10.3	5.2	4.7
	320	19.1	9.0	10.0
	325	25.3	12.4	12.7
	350	32.9	15.5	18.2

decreased, the dehydration reaction was enhanced to a marked extent over the doped catalysts. Batta *et al.*³ have already shown that poisoning the catalyst with other anions did not affect the selectivity (the ratio of acetone to propene in the catalysate) of NiO and ZnO catalysts. From the dependence of the various rates on temperature, the activation energies for the processes were calculated and are presented in Table 4. This table also compares the catalysts with respect to their activity at 305° and 300° respectively for NiO and ZnO sets of catalysts, and at WHSV⁻¹ of 1.5 hr. To bring out the correlation between catalytic and electrical properties, Table 4 also gives the changes in the electrical conductivity of NiO and ZnO catalysts accompanying SO₃ doping.

The effect of acetone and hydrogen, the products in the dehydrogenation of isopropanol, on the rate of dehydrogenation is shown in Table 5. Over NiO, the extent of dehydrogenation is reduced by about 25% by the addition of acetone at both the temperatures studied. On the other hand, the addition of acetone does not influence the rate of dehydrogenation

3. I. Batta, S. Bocsok, F. Solymosi and Z. G. Szabo, *Proc. Int. Congr. Catalysis*, 3rd, Amsterdam, 1964, 2, 1340 (Pub. 1965).

TABLE 4

Correlation between Catalytic and Electrical Properties of NiO and ZnO in the Decomposition of Isopropanol

Catalyst	Changes in Conductivity	Decomposition of Isopropanol over the catalysts						
		$E_{Cond.}$ kcal.	E_{Total} kcal/mole	E_{-H_2} kcal/mole	E_{-H_2O} kcal/mole	Total activity* mole %	Specific activity mole % per m ²	Selectivity H ₂ / propene
NiO	Ref.	13.7	8.2	8.2	—	44.9	2.06	—
NiO+0.5 mole % SO ₃	decreases	—	11.7	10.4	21.3	36.3	1.81	5.03
NiO+1.4 mole % SO ₃	decrease	—	14.4	12.0	17.7	28.6	1.55	2.75
NiO+2.7 mole % SO ₃	decreases	16.9	16.2	18.1	14.2	23.5	1.52	1.73
ZnO	Ref.	8.2	18.8	18.7	—	21.6	2.35	—
ZnO+0.5 mole % SO ₃	decreases	—	22.1	20.2	28.7	16.8	1.45	14.2
ZnO+1.3 mole % SO ₃	decreases	—	24.3	32.1	20.5	11.0	0.77	3.70
ZnO+2.8 mole % SO ₃	decreases	9.2	—	—	18.4	10.3	0.65	1.11

* 300° for ZnO, and 305° for NiO catalysts; WHSV⁻¹ = 1.5 hr.

TABLE 5

Influence of Acetone and Hydrogen on the Rate of Dehydrogenation of Isopropanol
WHSV⁻¹ = 0.05 hr.

Catalyst	Temp. °C	Acetone formed in mole per 100 moles of feed		
		No diluent	Diluent	
			Acetone*	Hydrogen
NiO	250	28.5	21.2	28.9
NiO	265	35.1	23.6	24.7
ZnO	300	25.3	24.5	25.1
ZnO	315	29.8	29.2	29.5

* Isopropanol was mixed with 2% by weight of acetone and passed over the catalyst.

over ZnO. To bring out the effect of hydrogen on the rate of dehydrogenation of isopropanol on NiO and ZnO, the catalysts were pretreated with hydrogen, in one set of experiments, at fixed temperature and at low pressures. There was no marked change in the yield of acetone over these catalysts. In another set of experiments, hydrogen was passed at a very low partial pressure along with isopropanol over the catalysts. The results in Table 5 refer to this set of experiments.

Conductivity Measurements : When the catalysts were exposed to isopropanol vapours in the temperature range 250°–360° (250–320° for NiO and 300°–360° for ZnO) the resulting changes in the electrical conductivity amounted to several orders of magnitude. Fig. 1

shows for two different temperatures, that the conductivity reaches a constant value after about 10 min. Whereas the conductivity of NiO decreases, ZnO exhibits an opposite trend. In both the cases the alcohol was fed at a constant rate of 1 ml per hr. per g. of the catalyst.

Fig. 1. Change in the electrical conductivity σ , of NiO and ZnO in the presence of isopropanol vapours.

The simultaneous effect of isopropanol and acetone on the electrical conductivity of NiO has also been studied. The apparatus was evacuated and a current of isopropanol was introduced at 250°. After the conductivity had attained a constant value, vapours of acetone were introduced. From Fig. 2, it is seen that either no conductivity changes or only very

Fig. 2. Simultaneous effect of isopropanol and acetone on the electrical conductivity of NiO, Temp. 250°.

slight ones were observed when the concentration of the gas phase was changed. A similar trend was observed in the case of acetone vapours being introduced followed by isopropanol vapours.

Changes in the electrical conductivity of NiO in the presence of isopropanol and hydrogen have been followed at 250° (Fig. 3). On introducing hydrogen, the conductivity dropped. When the flow was stopped and the apparatus was evacuated, the initial conductivity was restored. Subsequent addition produced the same effect and when isopropanol vapours

Fig. 3. Simultaneous effect of hydrogen and isopropanol on the electrical conductivity of NiO, Temp. 250°.

were also passed with hydrogen, further decrease in conductivity was observed. When the conductivity reached a constant value, the flow of hydrogen was stopped. There was no change in the conductivity. This condition was maintained if hydrogen was once again added to isopropanol vapours. When the current of alcohol vapours was cut off and only hydrogen was allowed to pass through, the conductivity increased again. These results are completely in agreement with those of Bielanski⁴.

The influence of acetone on the electrical conductivity of NiO and ZnO was very similar to that of isopropanol. In the case of NiO, exposing a surface previously treated with alcohol vapours to hydrogen caused a marked increase in conductivity. No such effects were observed when acetone vapours were passed over the surface of NiO previously treated with alcohol vapours. Over ZnO, on the other hand, when vapours of hydrogen as well as acetone were passed over a surface previously treated with alcohol vapours, they decreased the conductivity.

Dehydrogenation of β -pinene to p-cymene: β -Pinene, a constituent of the Indian turpentine oil, was dehydrogenated over oxidised and reduced chromia catalysts. The data are shown in Table 6. For the reactions over the reduced catalyst, the chromia gel was

4. A. Bielanski, in 'Catalysis and Chemical Kinetics', Academic Press Inc., New York, 1964, p. 93.

reduced with dry hydrogen for 5 hrs. at 450°C prior to reactions. Hydrogen was replaced by dry air for the reaction over the oxidised catalyst. The nature of electrical conductivity of oxidised and reduced chromia is also given in Table 6.

TABLE 6

Correlation between the Electrical and Catalytic Properties of Chromia in the Dehydrogenation of β -Pinene

Catalyst	Nature of conductivity	Amount of Cymene : moles/100 moles fed*			
		360°	410°	430°	460°
Cr ₂ O ₃ oxidised	<i>p</i> -type	7	17	18	32
Cr ₂ O ₃ reduced	<i>n</i> -type	18	24	30	45

* WHSV⁻¹ = 0.5 hr.

DISCUSSION

Decomposition of isopropanol: The catalytic dehydrogenation of isopropanol may consist of the following stages:—

Hydrogen does not affect the rate of dehydrogenation over both NiO and ZnO catalysts. Only a small portion of the surface area is covered with hydrogen. In addition, the dehydrogenation of isopropanol can proceed even on a surface covered with hydrogen (Fig. 3). These results indicate that under the conditions of alcohol dehydrogenation, the rate constant k_3 for the desorption of hydrogen is much greater than the rate constant k'_3 for its adsorption. Similar kinetic results were obtained by Balandin⁵ and Bielanski *et al.*⁶. Teichner and his coworkers⁷ arrived at the same conclusion for ZnO catalysts.

5. A. A. Balandin, *Adv. Catalysis*, 1958, **10**, 96.
6. A. Bielanski, J. Deren, J. Haber and J. Sloczynski, *Bull. acad. polon sci., Ser. sci., Chim. Geol. et Geograph.*, 1959, **7**, 333.
7. S. J. Teichner and Y. Dechatre, *Bull. Soc. Chim. France*, 1967, 2804.

In contrast to hydrogen, the addition of acetone to isopropanol considerably retards the rate of its dehydrogenation over NiO (Table 5). Thus, over NiO, the rate constant k_4 for the desorption of acetone must be much smaller than the rate constant k'_4 for the adsorption of acetone and the surface concentration of acetone cannot be very small. It should be mentioned here that over NiO, the rate of decomposition of isopropanol was found to be independent of its partial pressure under the reaction conditions. Presumably, the surface of NiO is saturated with alcohol molecules during the reaction. Thus the rate constant k_1 for the adsorption of the alcohol cannot be the controlling factor over NiO.

Depending on the relative magnitudes of k_2 and k_4 , the surface will be covered predominantly by alcohol molecules (k_2 smaller than k_4) or by acetone molecules (k_4 smaller than k_2). The electrical conductivity of NiO changes in the same direction by the introduction of alcohol, acetone or hydrogen. However, exposing a surface previously treated with alcohol vapours to acetone, caused no change in the electrical conductivity of the sample (Fig. 2). This implies that vapours of acetone do not cause total or partial desorption of alcohol and/or the products of its decomposition. As suggested by Bielanski⁴, this behaviour indicates two possibilities: either the chemisorbed isopropanol molecules are desorbed and the number of adsorbed acetone molecules happen to acquire just the value corresponding to the same conductivity changes as in the presence of isopropanol vapours, or the isopropanol immediately upon adsorption is decomposed into quickly desorbing hydrogen and slowly desorbing acetone which saturates the surface to the same extent as when in contact with acetone vapours. The former possibility is unlikely. Thus, the desorption of acetone is the slow rate-determining step in the overall process in NiO.

Over ZnO, the rate of dehydrogenation is unaffected by added acetone or hydrogen (Table 5). The rate constant k_3 and k_4 are, therefore, quite large for ZnO and cannot be the controlling factors for the dehydrogenation process. Between k_1 and k_2 representing the adsorption and the surface reaction of the alcohol respectively, Wolkenstein¹ considers the former to be the rate controlling factor.

In the presence of isopropanol vapours, the electrical conductivity of NiO decreases while that of ZnO increases. The change in the electrical conductivity in the course of the reaction may be due to two causes. In the first case, during the reaction process, coverage of the surface by the reagents gradually decreases and coverage by the products increases. In other words, the nature and concentration of the adsorbate change. This will be reflected in the changes in the electrical conductivity of the specimen during the reaction. During the dehydrogenation of isopropanol over NiO, acetone accumulates on the surface, since its desorption is a slow process. The decrease in the conductivity of NiO is thus due to the adsorbed acetone molecules. Such a decrease is possible only if the adsorbed acetone molecules transfer electrons to the solid thus increasing the electrochemical potential of the electrons in the solid.

A second cause responsible for the change in electrical conductivity during the reaction is the change in the chemical composition of the catalyst itself during the course of the reaction. The extent of the stoichiometric change increases as the reaction progresses. This

change will be reflected in its electrical conductivity. The increase in the electrical conductivity of ZnO during the dehydrogenation of methyl alcohol was attributed by Boreskov⁸ to a reduction of the catalyst under the influence of methyl alcohol vapour. ZnO being an *n*-type semiconductor, any surface reduction involving transfer of electrons to the solid will result in an increase in the electrical conductivity of the solid. The increase in the electrical conductivity of ZnO in the presence of isopropanol observed in the present investigation is attributed to a similar mechanism.

Influence of SO₃: Impregnated SO₃ decreases the electrical conductivity of both NiO and ZnO. The activation energy increases with the extent of SO₃ doping for total decomposition, dehydrogenation and for electrical conductivity (Table 4). The decrease in the electrical conductivity is seen to parallel the decrease in catalytic activity especially the formation of acetone. The dehydrogenation reaction is suppressed and a dehydration process is introduced, being enhanced as the amount of impregnated SO₃ increases. This is revealed by the fall in the selectivity ratio (Table 4).

Volkenstein¹ has classified all reactions into two classes: (i) reactions which proceed all the more rapidly, the higher the Fermi level. These are reactions accelerated by electrons (acceptor or *n*-class). (ii) reactions whose rates are greater the lower the Fermi level, and accelerated by holes (donor or *p*-class). Our results on the influence of SO₃ on the rate of dehydrogenation of isopropanol over ZnO support the assignment of dehydrogenation of alcohol to the former class. SO₃ suppresses the Fermi level, thus decreasing the reaction rate and the *n*-type conductivity.

NiO contains substantial amounts of oxygen strongly chemisorbed on the surface as O₂⁻ and O²⁻. The amount of excess oxygen is decreased by added SO₃ (Table 1). Chemisorbed oxygen localizes the electrons in the form of O₂⁻ and O²⁻ ions. Replacement of the oxygen by SO₃ releases these electrons and leads to a decrease in the *p*-type conductivity of NiO. SO₃ thus appears in the role of a donor impurity. Volkenstein⁹ points out that these donor impurities will tend to convert an acceptor reaction into a donor one. This will also explain the suppression of dehydrogenation by added SO₃. Since donor reactions are poisoned by donor impurities⁹, the retarding effect of SO₃ is quite understandable.

Dehydrogenation of β-pinene: Chromia being an amphoteric semiconductor, the nature of the semiconductivity depends on the pretreatment and other experimental conditions. During the reduction of the catalyst in hydrogen at 450°, the surface chromium ions of valency higher than 3 are reduced to the tri- and divalent states. Reduced chromia containing Cr²⁺ ions is an electron rich *n*-type semiconductor. Dehydrogenation is an acceptor type reaction accelerated by a high Fermi level in the solid. The greater rate of dehydrogenation of β-pinene over the reduced rather than the oxidised catalyst (Table 6) is, therefore, not surprising.

Two of us (AVR and PR) thank the CSIR for research fellowships. The work was done in the CSIR Unit 'Chemisorption and Catalysis'.

Department of Chemistry,
Loyola College,
Madras-34.

Received 21 September, 1970.

8. G. K. Boreskov and K. I. Matveyev, *Problemy Kinetiki i Kataliza*, 1955, **3**, 165.

9. Reference 1, p. 76.